

Navigating the policy landscape for managed aquifer recharge and reclaimed water use in Europe

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ABSTRACT

The impacts of climate change on groundwater worldwide have led to the discourse on sustainable groundwater management gaining currency over the last decades. One sustainable groundwater management strategy is managed aquifer recharge (MAR), particularly in situations of water scarcity. This paper analyzes the EU policy framework governing the implementation of MAR, groundwater management, and the reuse of reclaimed water. The findings show that MAR is not explicitly recognized in the EU water policy framework. We discuss the legal and administrative barriers that this policy landscape presents for MAR implementation. Our findings translate into five key actions at EU level: (1) explicit recognition of MAR practices within relevant directives; (2) harmonization across lists of pollutants regarding the purpose of water reuse, including for MAR; (3) a coherent and inter-operational risk monitoring strategy (and infrastructure) across Member States; (4) clear licensing and operational procedures (harmonized) across Member States; and (5) clarity across different directives in the promotion of reclaimed water as source water for MAR.

1. Introduction

Over the past few decades, due to rapid population growth, urbanization, and climate change, water demand has increased significantly, resulting in groundwater depletion and contamination (Alam et al., 2021; Arshad et al., 2025; Dahlke et al., 2018). According to Richey et al. (2015), 21 of 37 major aquifers worldwide are already depleted. Groundwater depletion is the primary cause of global water scarcity and other environmental issues (Alam et al., 2021; Famiglietti and Rodell, 2013; Leijnse et al., 2024). For example, excess groundwater pumping can indirectly contribute to sea-level rise, since a portion of the abstracted groundwater eventually reaches the oceans through rivers or runoff (Wada et al., 2010). While this contribution is smaller than that

from ice melt and thermal expansion, it remains a quantifiable component of ongoing sea-level rise (IPCC, 2022). The rapid decline of groundwater has increased pumping costs, leading to dried-up wells, reduced groundwater discharge to springs, decreased base flow, and accelerated seawater intrusion, which subsequently affect the ecosystem (de Graaf et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2026).

Groundwater is a crucial source of drinking water and irrigation (Alam et al., 2021), accounting for approximately 75% of the EU water supply.¹ Therefore, with the growing demand for irrigation and public water supply, and the worsening of groundwater quality and quantity worldwide, the discussion on Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) has been renewed as a promising solution for ensuring water security and protecting freshwater. The new developments in MAR offer a

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¹ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/groundwater_en

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multi-objective water treatment approach, focusing on advanced technologies and unconventional water sources that not only provide water storage but also enhance water quality, thereby strengthening water security and resilience. Therefore, MAR can help to enhance groundwater quality and quantity, as well as prevent groundwater pollution (Abdalla and Al-Rawahi, 2013; Alam et al., 2021; Masciopinto, 2013).

In line with the *EU Water Resilience Strategy*, which seeks to reduce water consumption and increase water recycling (European Commission, 2025b), this paper focuses on the reuse of reclaimed water as source water for MAR. Reclaimed water is urban wastewater that has been treated for reuse or recycling.² Once the aquifer has been recharged, reclaimed water can be repurposed for various applications (reuse). Two of the most common (re)uses for this water are irrigation and drinking water. To mitigate health and environmental risks associated with water pollution and to ensure the safe reuse of reclaimed water, it must be managed within a robust risk management framework. Reclaimed water is already reused as a water source for MAR in several European countries, such as Spain, France, Cyprus, Italy, Portugal, and Belgium.³

Amid the ongoing water crisis, MAR is becoming increasingly relevant, particularly in areas with water scarcity pressures. However, earlier studies indicated that European water policies do not explicitly recognize it (Wintgens et al., 2009), leaving MAR without a clear legal framework, presenting challenges for its implementation (Burchi, 2014). This paper analyzes the main EU water policies and highlights the main legislative challenges to MAR implementation. It provides a comprehensive analysis of the European Union (EU) water policy framework governing MAR, with special emphasis on reclaimed water as source water. The paper carefully addresses the intersection of EU water policy, MAR, and the use of reclaimed water.

At the European Union (EU) level, policies are formulated through directives, regulations, and laws formally accepted in agreement with EU Member States. Once in place, these regulatory instruments must be transposed by Member States into national and regional legislation. *EU Regulations* and *EU Decisions* have a direct, binding effect on Member States, while *EU Directives* offer some flexibility in the form and method of implementation but entail a legal obligation to comply in full (Haverland and Romeijn, 2007).

The EU, through Horizon Europe, has funded several projects to develop innovative tools and strategies for groundwater management. Several of these EU-financed projects⁴ exploring groundwater management have increasingly highlighted the policy and governance challenges associated with MAR implementation (Baruffi et al., 2013). MAR-related EU projects have presented overviews of the EU water policy framework regulating MAR, outlining relevant EU Directives and Regulations (Burchi, 2014; De Giglio et al., 2018), but with limited analysis of the interrelations among these policies and their specific implications for MAR. This paper identifies indirect references to MAR in key EU regulatory instruments that provide the policy context in which MAR currently operates, given the absence of an explicit policy framework that addresses MAR. It was undertaken within the context of the MAR2PROTECT Horizon Europe project (2022–2026), which aims to provide an innovative, holistic approach to enhancing groundwater resources and preventing groundwater contamination.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the

methodology used for the policy analysis. Section 3 contains the results of the analysis of EU water management policies and the conditions they set for MAR. Section 4 presents the main issues related to the transposition of the EU water policy framework influencing the implementation of MAR in Member States. Section 5 discusses the research findings. Section 6 concludes with final reflections.

2. Methodology

Identifying water policies that directly or indirectly address MAR is complex, as different policies apply to various sources of water and their potential uses. Therefore, this paper uses an analytical framework that distinguishes EU water policy framework according to the different stages of MAR implementation in Europe. This framework divides MAR implementation into three interrelated domains. The first domain concerns the policies governing the water source used to recharge the aquifer. A particular emphasis is placed on the use of reclaimed water as a water source. The second domain addresses policy issues related to artificial aquifer storage, including the extraction of stored water once the aquifer has been recharged. The third domain covers water policies that influence govern the potential reuse of water, including the quality requirements for reused water and the various uses to which it may be put. This is illustrated in Fig. 1, where MAR serves as the central block in the water management strategy explored in this paper, with the other policy domains addressing issues related to water sources and water reuse. Moreover, the policies concerning pollutants (including their measurement and monitoring) are included horizontally, covering policies governing both reclaimed water as a source and its reuse.

The paper is based on extensive desk research. Data collection for the analysis began by identifying critical documents on water policies at the EU level. These documents were searched for at *EUR-Lex*. In addition, a review of academic articles and project reports on policy issues influencing MAR implementation was conducted. The academic literature was searched in *Web of Science* using keywords including *groundwater, legislation, aquifer, regulation, Europe*. This search resulted in 51 articles. From this search, the abstracts were read, and only those addressing EU policies regarding groundwater were retained, resulting in a selection of 12 articles. The search was complemented with a snowball approach, in which citations in the selected articles were identified and included in the analysis. The search for project documents was conducted using Google Search with the exact keywords: *groundwater recharge, Europe, MAR, and aquifer*.

In addition, two EU databases were consulted: WISE, which provides information from Member States on the adaptation of the EU Water policy in their national legislation, and the EU Infringement Procedures Database, to compile information on the delay in transposing elements indirectly linked to MAR implementation. See Table 1.

Particular focus was placed on academic publications stemming from previous EU projects that addressed EU policies influencing groundwater recharge.⁵ As a macro (EU) level analysis, the list of water management policies analyzed in this paper is extensive (i.e., covering Directives and Regulations addressing the reuse of reclaimed water for MAR as well as the use of MAR water). As such, it does not include guidance, implementing acts, standards, or Member State-level interpretative practices that effectively function as law in action.

² Wastewater is the used water of a community or industry that contains dissolved and suspended matter.

³ <https://water.europa.eu/freshwater/europe-freshwater/water-reuse>

⁴ DEMEAU (<https://www.un-igrac.org/donor-partner/demeau>), Pwales (<https://www.interreg-europe.eu/good-practices/pwales-managed-aquifer-recharge-mar>), and MARSOL (<https://www.santannapisa.it/en/node/5314>).

⁵ Most academic articles use titles without acronyms. Therefore, by using the keyword 'aquifer', we identified papers addressing aquifer recharge and MAR.

⁶ See for example De Giglio et al. (2018); Fernandez Escalante et al. (2020); Martinez Fernandez et al. (2020); Miret et al. (2012); Pulido Velazquez and Ward (2017).

Fig. 1. Analytical framework for the policy analysis of MAR's legal framework. Source: the authors

Table 1 Description of main documents used in the analysis.

Type of document	Number	Description
EU Directives	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water Framework Directive (WFD) Groundwater Directive (GWD) Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) Drinking Water Directive (DWD) Environmental Liability Directive (ELD, 2004/35/EC) Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (EIA 2014/52/EU)
EU Regulations	1	Waste Water Regulation (WWR)
EU Databases	2	WISE Water Framework Directive Database EU Infringement Procedures Database
Academic papers	47	From Web of Science + snowball selection
MAR-related EU project reports	5	Diverse EU-financed Horizon Europe projects addressing MAR implementation + ZP4W policy working group discussions

Source: the authors.

3. Analysis of water-related EU policies

An overview of the current European water policy framework governing the implementation of MAR in the Member States is presented in Fig. 2. The specific policies are discussed per policy domain in the sections below.

3.1. EU water management and MAR

The implementation of MAR is enabled by the Groundwater Directive (GWD, 2006/118/EC), which protects groundwater by establishing standards and thresholds for pollutants in groundwater (WFD, 2000). The GWF falls under the Water Framework Directive (WFD, 2000/60/EC), which is considered the European Water Policy. The WFD protects EU water bodies from pollution, prioritizing aquatic ecosystems and water quality as key elements in water management decisions (Martinez Fernandez et al., 2020; Pulido Velazquez and Ward, 2017; WFD, 2000). These two directives allow for several water management strategies to be implemented in Member States. One of them is the intentional recharge of aquifers or groundwater bodies, currently referred to as MAR.

MAR is a water management strategy that not only stabilizes groundwater levels and helps mitigate land subsidence caused by aquifer depletion, but also but also reduces the contribution of excess groundwater abstraction to sea-level rise (Dillon et al., 2019). It has played a crucial role in restoring the groundwater balance by increasing available groundwater, controlling groundwater depletion, and

improving groundwater quality (Burchi, 2014; Dawoud, 2024; Gale and Dillon, 2005). Its importance is increasingly recognized, as it has the potential to contribute to more than 10% of global groundwater extraction. Worldwide, MAR has been implemented in approximately 62 countries at around 1200 sites (Stefan and Ansems, 2018). In Europe, it has been successfully adopted since the 1960s. Based on the list of Sprenger et al. (2017), IGRAC's inventory of 280 MAR schemes in the EU, and in the **Supplementary materials (Table A)**, MAR schemes using reclaimed water as a water source are presented.

Nevertheless, the implementation of MAR is challenging because the EU water policy framework governing MAR is not harmonized with respect to MAR (Burchi, 2014). The first issue of relevance is that the current EU water policy does not explicitly refer to MAR; instead, it uses terms such as *aquifer recharge or reinjection*, and *groundwater augmentation*, but not *MAR per se*. A second legislative challenge is that EU water policy only refers to MAR indirectly or as a supplementary measure. The Water Framework Directive (WFD) indirectly recognizes MAR as one of the several instruments for sustainable water management to achieve and maintain good groundwater status (WFD, 2000). In the case of the Groundwater Directive (GWD), MAR is recognized as a *supplementary measure* to protect groundwater against pollution and deterioration (GWD, 2006). A third important challenge is the indirect reference to the intention of aquifer recharge in both the WFD and the GWD. None of these directives mentions *intentional or managed aquifer recharge* and only refers to *aquifer recharge or reinjection*. Therefore, the *intention* of the recharge is implicitly stated in both directives through the requirement for prior authorizations by the authorities of Member States (European Commission, 2025a, 2025c). Both directives require that all injections or recharge into groundwater bodies require a permit, authorization, or license, confirming the implicit assumption of intentional aquifer recharge. This issue is a practical bottleneck for the implementation of MAR in EU Member States, since the procedure for these authorizations is unclear as it is translated into the local level.

An additional challenge for implementing MAR is that although the legislative instrument for its national legislation is specified in the EU directives, the specific means for implementing it are not. The WFD and the GWD establish the principles and guidelines for sustainable groundwater governance and management, but not the specific means (Bixio et al., 2006). The WFD (2000) recognizes the *river basin* as the primary unit for water management and planning, explicitly instructing that national water [including groundwater] policies should be operationalized through *River Basin Management Plans* (RBMPs). Therefore, by mandate, the RBMPs are the legislative enablers for the implementation of MAR at the national level (see Table 2). As indicated in the WFD, each RBMP should establish a Flood Risk Management Plan (FRMP) and Natural Water Retention Measures (NWRM), which serve as

Fig. 2. EU policies influencing Managed Aquifer Recharge. Source: the authors

Table 2
EU water management policy framework (main directives).

Name	Objective	Mention of Aquifer Recharge	Legislative Unit for MAR's implementation
WFD (2000/60/EC)	To protect and enhance the quality of Europe's water resources, benefiting both the environment and human health. By 2027, the quality of all waters (surface water and groundwater) throughout Europe must be both chemically and ecologically sound.	Article 11(3) and Article 11(4). Annex VI (Part B) MAR cannot be approved if it leads to failure in improving water quality, or if it causes its deterioration Art 4(7)	RBMP (should include FRMP and NWRM)
GWD (2006/118/EC)	To prevent and control groundwater pollution.	Article 6(3d)	RBMP (should include FRMP and NWRM)
ELD (2004/35/EC)	To establish a common EU framework for the prevention and remedying of environmental damage at a reasonable cost to society. In the case of groundwater, it refers to the WFD objectives.	n.a. Annex II discusses groundwater remediations.	Remedial measures should be carried out by operators with the approval and agreement of the authorities of the Member States.
EID (2011/92/EU including amendment EIA 2014/52/EU)	To assess the environmental effect of certain projects before they are authorized.	Annex I(11) includes artificial groundwater recharge equal to or larger than 10 million m3 Annex II(I) includes artificial groundwater recharge not included in Annex I.	EIA and/or threshold criteria (set by Member States) should be carried out before commencing.

Source: the authors.

indirect entry points for MAR implementation.⁷ Each of the three cycles of the RBMP under the WFD has a 6-year planning horizon (i.e., 2009–2015, 2016–2021, and 2022–2027). **Table B** in the **Supplementary materials** presents currently open infringement procedures regarding RBMPs, illustrating the challenges Member States face in transposing EU guidelines into their national legislation.

Other important pieces of the EU policy framework that indirectly enable the implementation of MAR are the Environmental Liability Directive (ELD, 2004/35/EC) and the Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (EIA 2014/52/EU). The EIA ensures that projects or interventions likely to have a significant environmental impact are adequately assessed before approval, whereas the ELD requires the prevention and remediation of groundwater pollution (ELD, 2004). In the case of the EIA, Annex I(11) and Annex II(I) include *artificial groundwater recharge* schemes in the list of interventions requiring assessment. The EIA does not refer to MAR per se, but the types of artificial recharge mentioned in Annex I and II indirectly refer to MAR as

an approach for recharge. Similar to the GWD, the ELD does not explicitly mention MAR, but it mandates the prevention and remediation of groundwater quantity and quality (ELD, 2004). Therefore, it (indirectly) allows MAR as a solution for preventing groundwater contamination.

There are several types of MAR interventions;⁸ however, the EU water policy framework does not differentiate among them and refers to *aquifer recharge* in general. Therefore, this paper refers to MAR without differentiating among MAR intervention types. **Table 2** presents the main EU Directives that constitute the framework for MAR implementation, along with the unit responsible for their legislative implementation.

⁸ The most common MAR interventions are: riverbank filtration (RBF), soil-aquifer treatment (SAT), aquifer recharge and recovery (ARR), aquifer storage and recovery (ASR), aquifer storage, transfer, and recovery (ASTR), and direct injection (IGRAC, 2007).

⁷ See Technical report no. 82 for more details.

Table 3
EU policy framework related to water sources for MAR.

Name	Source water for MAR	Reference	Implications for MAR
WFD (2000/60/EC)	"The use of the source does not compromise the achievement of the environmental objectives established for the source or the recharged or augmented body of groundwater."	Article 11 (3f)	RBMPs should establish monitoring controls to ensure that the water source for MAR complies with the groundwater quality standards.
WFD (2000/60/EC)	"Member States shall implement the measures necessary to prevent or limit the input of pollutants into groundwater and to prevent the deterioration of the status of all bodies of groundwater, ..."	Article 4(1) (b)(i)	RBMPs should outline pollution-prevention actions to prevent MAR-related groundwater contamination.
GWD (2006/118/EC)	"In order to achieve the objective of preventing or limiting inputs of pollutants into groundwater, ..., Member States shall ensure that: (a) all measures necessary to prevent inputs into groundwater of any hazardous substances, ... (b) for pollutants ... which are not considered hazardous, ... all measures necessary to limit inputs into groundwater so as to ensure that such inputs do not cause deterioration or significant and sustained upward trends in the concentration of pollutants in groundwater."	Article 6(1)	MAR authorizations issued by Member States should include requirements to ensure that MAR activities do not result in groundwater deterioration.
GWD (2006/118/EC)	"...Member States may be exempted from the measures required by paragraph 1 inputs of pollutants that are: ... (d) the result of artificial recharge or augmentation of bodies of groundwater authorised in accordance with Article 11(3)(f) of Directive 2000/60/EC"	Article 6(3) (d)	Excludes the obligation to avoid or limit inputs of pollutants in the case of MAR, but this needs to be performed in accordance with the WFD

Source: the authors.

3.2. Reclaimed water as source water for MAR

Water sources for MAR include the reuse of reclaimed water. Although the type of source water for MAR is not explicitly stated in any EU policy document, the WFD states that the water source used must meet its environmental objectives. In other words, any source water for MAR should comply with the WFD's environmental objectives and should not result in groundwater deterioration (WFD, 2000). In addition, the GWD indicates that recharge should use water derived from surface or groundwater and not compromise the achievement of the environmental objectives of these directives (GWD, 2006). See Table 3.

The use of reclaimed water as source water in MAR is not (explicitly) included nor excluded, in either the WFD or the GWD (Wintgens et al., 2009). It is an increasingly adopted practice, yet also controversial due to the risk of aquifer contamination by the recharged water, as well as the potential for clogging by the injected water. Also, MAR is not explicitly designed to remove pollutants, and the factors affecting the filtration of pollutants into groundwater used for drinking water supplies are not yet fully understood (Mumberg et al., 2024). Nevertheless, some authors indicated that pollutant transport during MAR to groundwater systems is limited, and more quantitative and qualitative studies are needed, as risk analyses applied to MAR are not yet standardized (Mumberg et al., 2024), particularly when discussing the reuse of reclaimed water as source water for MAR, and considering the different MAR types and on-site soil characteristics.

The reuse of reclaimed water is part of the *EU Circular Economy Action Plan*, which aims to promote its use for irrigation to enhance resource efficiency and address water scarcity. There are two relevant pieces of EU water policy regarding the reuse of reclaimed water that influence its use as a source water for MAR. First, the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD 91/271/EEC, recast in November 2024) regulates the treatment of urban wastewater to protect public health and the environment from inadequately treated wastewater (UWWTD, 2024). As with the WFD and the GWD, the UWWTD recast does not explicitly refer to MAR, but it does state the necessary conditions for the [potential] use of reclaimed water reuse in aquifers (see Table 4).

Secondly, the Waste Water Regulation (WWR, 2020/741) formalizes the use of reclaimed water, particularly for agricultural purposes. It mandates *Water Reuse Risk Management Plans* (WRRMPs) for facilities that use reclaimed water to identify and control health and environmental risks, and to specify quality and monitoring requirements (WWR, 2020). The WWR supports the UWWTD requirement to reuse wastewater whenever appropriate by promoting and establishing minimum conditions for the reuse of reclaimed water in agriculture and providing

guidelines for implementing the zero pollution policy package agreed upon under the *EU Green Deal* (WWR, 2020).⁹ Table 4 presents the main EU documents that influence the use of reclaimed water in MAR. It summarizes their primary objective, the unit of implementation, and the implications for implementing MAR.

3.3. MAR – aquifer storage

A relevant use of MAR is for environmental protection and restoration. By recharging aquifers or replenishing groundwater, MAR maintains ecological quality and builds hydraulic barriers against saltwater intrusion (Cordeiro et al., 2023), controls salinity and land subsidence (Shi et al., 2016), and reduces groundwater distress levels. In these cases, the implementation of MAR is also influenced by the Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC (Annex II), which addresses special conservation zones.

3.4. MAR water (re)use

For all water management strategies, the GWD requires risk management plans (RMPs). Therefore, MAR schemes should be planned and implemented with consideration of the ecosystems and environmental setting of the MAR site.¹⁰ This applies not only to the water source of MAR but also to the (re)use of this groundwater. In some cases, MAR water is reused for domestic purposes, such as drinking water. In this case, the Drinking Water Directive (DWD 2020/2184) is the primary European policy addressing drinking water pollution, setting standards and thresholds to improve the quality of drinking water.¹¹ Therefore, MAR's RMPs should comply with the requirements and obligations of the DWD.

⁹ *EU Procedure 2018/0169/COD* outlines the minimum requirements for the reuse of reclaimed water, specifying control measures for monitoring essential water quality parameters. *EU Regulation 2024/1765* provides technical specifications for the WRRMPs. Additionally, MAR schemes that reuse treated industrial wastewater should consider the regulations established in the *Industrial Emissions Directive (IED) 2010/75/EU*.

¹⁰ This assessment should be based on the specific conceptualization developed under the RBMPs based on the local geology, hydrogeology, soil type, and ecology of the sites (European Commission, 2025a).

¹¹ In the case of reclaimed water, its use for drinking water was first regulated in 1980 by the 80/778/EC and then in 1998 by the Council Directive 98/83/EC, which was substantially revised into the Drinking Water Directive (DWD EU 2015/1787) and in 2020 under DWD 2020/2184 (December 23, 2020).

Table 4
EU legal framework for the use of reclaimed water (implications for MAR).

Name	Type	Objective(s)	Unit of implementation	Implications for MAR
UWWTD	Directive	To protect human health and the environment from the effects of untreated urban wastewater	WWTPs	MAR is not directly mentioned in the UWWTD. However, it provides the policy mandate to reuse treated wastewater and provides legitimacy for water reuse in general. It also lists treatment requirements and conditions for the reuse of treated urban wastewater, including MAR.
WRR (2020/741)	Regulation	To establish minimum water quality and monitoring requirements for reclaimed urban wastewater to ensure its safe use	WWRMPs	The WRR does not directly refer to MAR. However, it promotes the reuse of reclaimed water when the quantitative status of groundwater bodies is under pressure. It requires a risk management plan and monitoring mechanisms to prevent groundwater pollution, as per the WFD.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

One of the most common uses of MAR water is irrigation. Reclaimed water for irrigation contains higher levels of organic and inorganic constituents and nutrients than freshwater, potentially reducing the need for fertilizers (Florides et al., 2024). This makes the adequate management of reclaimed water particularly relevant for agricultural purposes. The intentional reuse of MAR water for irrigation should comply with the minimum quality requirements set by the WWR (WWR, 2020). Another legal European instrument for the use of reclaimed water for irrigation is the *Guidelines for the Use of Treated Wastewater for Irrigation*, which is reflected in ISO/TC 282. A relevant EU policy in this regard is the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC), which outlines the requirements that must be met to prevent and reduce water pollution from nitrates and to protect EU waters from agricultural pressures.

Untreated wastewater can pose a risk to human health and pollute lakes, rivers, soil, and coastal and groundwater resources. The minimum requirements for reclaimed water quality depend on its intended reuse, including MAR. The UWWTD requires an *Integrated Urban Wastewater Management Plan* by 2033 for all areas with more than 100,000 inhabitants, and by 2028 for areas with 10,000 to 100,000 inhabitants (UWWTD, 2024). The Directive protects both water quality and human health by requiring Member States to collect and treat urban wastewater from all agglomerations of 2000 people or more before discharging it into the environment. According to the European Environment Agency, in 2022, about 81% of the EU population was connected to at least secondary wastewater treatment.¹² A large number of WWTPs do not yet achieve tertiary treatment, and it is in this segment that several MAR EU-funded projects have technical pilot proposals (e.g., MAR2PROTECT¹³ and MARSURE¹⁴). See Table 5.

However, at the regional/local level, the complexity of implementing or operationalizing the requirements and obligations mandated by the UWWTD is transferred to the wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). WWTPs are the key actors in treating urban wastewater in the Member States. The UWWTD outlines the minimum requirements that WWTPs must meet. The UWWTD recast requires large WWTDs to undergo quaternary treatment, focusing on the removal of micropollutants and Per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) (which were not required in previous versions of the UWWTD). In 2023 and 2024, sixteen EU Member States failed to comply with the UWWTD requirements, primarily because they did not conduct secondary treatment in their WWTPs prior to discharge.¹⁵ See Table B in the **Supplementary materials**.

4. Transposition of water management policies by EU member states

The transposition of EU mandates into the national legislation of Member States is a lengthy, complicated, and challenging process (Bourblanc et al., 2013; Thomann and Zgaga, 2024; Toshkov, 2007). The diverse levels of bureaucratic administration within Member States and the indirect reference to MAR in the EU water framework challenge the harmonization of its implementation. When focusing on the implementation of MAR at the Member State level, the RBMPs play a critical role (as stated by the WFD). Diverse EU evaluation reports on the transposition of WFD mandates through the RBMPs and FRMPs identify issues such as weak institutional coordination and bureaucratic challenges.¹⁶ These issues also challenge the implementation of MAR, which is carried out through operational units within the RBMPs and FRMPs of Member States. Failure to present updated RBMPs in accordance with the WFD and the EU Green Deal has led to infringement proceedings against several EU Member States (see **Supplementary materials**).¹⁷ Some of the major problems in fulfilling this requirement include the delays of Member States' with the review, adoption, and reporting on RBMPs and TFRMP Plans.¹⁸ See Table C in the **Supplementary materials**.

As previously mentioned, MAR interventions address local contexts that are often regulated by multiple governance layers and jurisdictions, and they frequently lack adequate local water resource management plans (Dillon et al., 2022). Such plans are crucial for establishing entitlements, allocations, obligations, and conditions for the use of water resources in MAR interventions. The absence of such plans constrains the implementation of MAR, which ensures adequate and transparent management of groundwater demand (Dillon et al., 2022).

Groundwater recharge requires a permit, license, or authorization under the WFD and the GWD. The actual implementation of MAR depends on the site's local characteristics. Therefore, the authorizations for any water management strategy depend on regional or local-level policies. This transfer of decision-making authority from the European level to the Member States is a critical characteristic of the WFD (Pulido Velazquez and Ward, 2017). Therefore, the implementation of MAR should be accompanied by local permit-granting processes and schemes based on risk assessment to protect human health. There are strong indications that these licensing or permit processes are not clearly established at the local or regional level in several Member States. For example, Standen et al. (2023) indicate that the pathway to obtain MAR licenses or permits in Portugal is unclear. This is supported by the findings of Sufyan et al. (2024) regarding the absence of specific legislation regarding licenses for MAR implementation in Italy.

¹² <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/european-zero-pollution-dashboards/indicators/population-connected-to-at-least-secondary-wastewater-treatment>

¹³ <https://mar2protect.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://www.water4all-partnership.eu/project/marsure>

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/EN/inf_22_3768

¹⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52007DC0128>

¹⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/implementing-eu-law/search-infringement-decisions/>

¹⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/EN/inf_23_4367

Table 5
Updated requirements of wastewater treatment under the UWWTD recast.

# P.E	Requirement for wastewater Discharges	Reference	Deadline for fulfillment of requirements	Implications for MAR
1000>x < 2000	Collective systems, Secondary treatment (or equivalent)	Article 6 (3)	2035	
x > 2000	Secondary treatment	Article 6	2037	
x > 10,000	Tertiary treatment, Quaternary treatment	Article 7 (3) Article 8 (4)	2045 2045	Most EU-funded MAR projects are currently addressing third treatments. However, several technologies developed by these projects do not address the pollutants corresponding to quaternary treatments.
x > 150,000	Tertiary treatment (or equivalent), Quaternary treatment	Article 7 Article 8	2039 2045	

Source: Elaborated by the authors with information from [UWWTD \(2024\)](#). Note: secondary treatment: to remove organic matter. Tertiary treatment: to remove nutrients and specific pollutants (i.e., nitrogen and phosphorus). Quaternary treatment: to remove micropollutants.

Another issue challenging the implementation of MAR is its still-controversial nature, and, even more so, the use of reclaimed water for aquifer recharge ([Louwyck et al., 2022](#); [Rivera-Vidal et al., 2025](#)). The lack of comprehensive data on groundwater issues across Member States is another factor in the slow adoption of MAR ([Chavez Garcia Silva et al., 2024](#)). Additionally, reclaimed water as source water requires licenses and permits from the Member States. Another important note in the requirement for the reuse of reclaimed water is the changing political environment at EU level, where the high standards and goals for clean water and zero pollution by 2027 are being challenged. According to [EEB \(2024\)](#), in response to high requirements by the EU, some Member States (e.g., the Netherlands, Germany, Denmark, Finland, and Luxembourg) are asserting their national rights to water management and seeking exceptions to the WFD's environmental and pollution standards. This implies that Member States have agreed to push back the legal deadline for compliance on PFAS and pharmaceuticals to 2039 and possibly further to 2051.

5. Discussion of findings

This section discusses the barriers and bottlenecks this policy landscape presents for MAR, particularly regarding policy complexity and implementation.

5.1. Policy complexity: multi-level, multi-actor

The analysis of the policy framework relating to MAR shows that most EU Member States adjust, modify, or (re)formulate national policies slowly to align their environmental objectives with those indicated by the European Commission through European-level Directives and Regulations. This is particularly challenging in terms of MAR implementation as MAR is not explicit in EU water policy framework. This translation between policies at the supra-national level and those at the national level is complex since each national policy is linked to other thematic policies, making it demanding to align national policies with those at the European level.

The process of policy alignment takes time (i.e., years) and is implemented gradually through policy amendments and the introduction of new water policies. It is important to note that policy implementation is carried out at the local level thereafter. Complexity increases as national-level policies are transposed to sub-national levels (e.g., regional, basin, municipal). The systemic interplay of these policies is not fully understood at the sub-national level, as evident in the academic literature ([Wanzenbock and Frenken, 2020](#)).

5.2. Challenges with river basin management plans (RBMPs)

European directives and regulations are designed as guidelines that establish minimum parameters to be adopted by EU Member States.

National policies are (re)formulated to create instruments that sub-national governments can implement. A critical example is the case of the RBMP, which is the unit of implementation of the EU water policy framework. The WFD requires RBMPs to include a detailed methodology, including definitions, assumptions, and approaches for evaluating the status of water quality and quantity. The GWD also indicates the RBMPs as the enablers for groundwater protection and remediation. However, translating this mandate at the local level is not straightforward, and implementing it in local water management plans has been challenging for EU Member States ([Gonzales del Campo et al., 2012](#); [Hammond Antwi, 2025](#)). FRMPs are elaborated regionally, taking into account the region's characteristics. However, their general structure and scope differ across countries and regions. The elaboration at the local level is relevant, as the RBMPs need to adjust their [implementation] content to the local needs; however, the methodology is not clearly stated in the EU directives, and therefore, the level of methodological detail varies across EU Member States' RBMPs. In addition, before designing the RBMPs, countries needed to adjust their national policies to enable the creation of River Basin Authorities (RBAs). Although the RBAs design the RBMPs at the subnational level, these plans require national approval, thereby increasing the complexity of interactions within the policy system. This complication has caused delays in EU Member States complying with the WFD ([EEB, 2024](#); [Hammond Antwi, 2025](#)).

5.3. Local implementation of wastewater treatment obligations

When the WWR was enforced in the EU in June 2023, Member States were prompted to revisit their national and sub-national legislation to adapt it to this concept and facilitate its implementation. Therefore, enforcing the reuse of reclaimed water still requires harmonization efforts among the different Member States' legal systems, water management practices, and social acceptance. The complexity and fragmentation of the existing regulative frameworks are a challenge for this transposition.

Although EU Member States are trying to rapidly change and adapt their national laws to the new EU requirements to reach the environmental objectives marked by the EU Green Deal and the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, the bottleneck is in the implementation, which is enabled by the RBMP and local/regional guidelines or strategic plans. ([Gonzales del Campo et al., 2012](#); [Hammond Antwi, 2025](#)). The transposition of EU directives into Member States' legal frameworks requires restructuring at the national and sub-national levels, particularly in terms of the structure of water resource/management planning, water quality environmental policy, and the organization of public/private water services providers ([Balzarolo et al., 2011](#)).

Reclaimed water is processed in WWTPs owned by the public or private sectors. Conventionally, WWTPs are the final destination of urban wastewater, with the traditional mandate to remove organic

matter, nutrients, suspended solids, and microorganisms. Therefore, they are the practical actors in implementing and accomplishing wastewater treatments, as indicated in the UWWTD. An important bottleneck identified in this paper concerns the role of WWTPs in implementing the UWWTD across the different Member States. The UWWTD is a cross-cutting policy indicating that Member States should collect wastewater (Art. 3), treat wastewater with at least a secondary treatment, and comply minimally with the treatment of organic matter in urban wastewater before reintroducing reclaimed water to the environment (Art. 4), and wastewater treated with a tertiary treatment (Art. 5). In practice, many of these WWTPs cannot fulfil this mandate to remove these pollutants when new lists of pollutants and value parameters are added to the legislation, as they require reinvestment to update their capacities. Additionally, the UWWTD recommends that Member States establish wastewater collection systems for all settlements with a population of 2000 or more inhabitants.

The adoption of the UWWTD by EU Member States has been slow, and Member States failed to comply with the UWWTD requirements in 2023 and 2024, primarily because they did not conduct secondary treatment before discharge. Therefore, with the 2024 amendments to this Directive, the requirement for tertiary and quaternary treatments places even greater pressure on local WWTPs in Member States. The stricter requirements for pollution control under the UWWTD recast present a greater opportunity to implement pilot technologies developed by EU-funded MAR projects focusing on tertiary and quaternary wastewater treatment as a source water for MAR.

5.4. Diverging lists of pollutants

The WFD, GWD, and MAR-related water policies define a baseline of pollutant lists and threshold values. Furthermore, each EU Directive related to the source of reclaimed water and to the reuse of water lists pollutants to be controlled. Yet it is challenging to translate these lists of pollutants into national and sub-national legislation: these lists and threshold values vary across national and sub-national levels as each EU Member State adapts them to its current legislation and infrastructure capacity. At the national level, legislation specifies the pollutants to be monitored and controlled. These lists are also present at the sub-national level in the RBMPs. However, there are discrepancies in the types of pollutants listed in the (sub)national legislations and their value parameters. Although progress is being made towards more harmonized lists and values, this process is lengthy, as (sub)national legislation must be adapted, infrastructure upgraded, and the costs (including monitoring) remain affordable (as mandated by the WFD).

Regarding the Pollutants of Emerging Concern (PEC), the EU watch lists are not entirely aligned with those included in (sub)national policies. The discrepancy between the list of PEC and those identified in EU directives is difficult to address during national transposition. This is due to the restrictive national rules already in place, the incomplete adoption of mechanisms needed to implement measures in national legislation, insufficient monitoring and technological capacity at the local level, and the potentially significant increase in associated costs.

While MAR interventions can monitor and predict future groundwater pollution through digital tools, the current set of pollutants addressed in MAR interventions is not aligned with those listed in supranational, national, or subnational policies. This divide in pollutants is a point of discussion between *in-situ* needs and top-down recommendations. Therefore, the need is either to open up the list of pollutants to local focus (e.g., by including mobile and toxic compounds) or to extend the list at the EU level.

5.5. Increased water consumption due to wastewater reuse

A critical element when considering MAR is the reuse of reclaimed water. The Action Plan for a Circular Economy through the WWR emphasizes the reuse of reclaimed water for various (non-)human activities

and uses. Reclaimed water should reach a quality level that reduces pollution and negative environmental impacts by reintroducing it to the water cycle. (Cordeiro et al., 2023). However, the intention is not to build a support mechanism to increase water consumption; rather, it aims to introduce reclaimed water for reuse as an alternative (Cordeiro et al., 2023). Although this is clear at the EU level through related water policies, including the Action Plan for Circular Economy, this objective is often lost when policy is framed at the sub-national level.

5.6. Challenges with monitoring and reporting

The WFD and the UWWTD require EU Member States to monitor and report regularly. The WFD requires EU Member States to report on the progress of their RBMPs every 6 years (the next report is due in 2027), particularly on the third cycle (2021–2027) of RBMPs and FRMPs. The UWWTD requires Member States to report on the achievement of wastewater treatment requirements for reuse, including the application of secondary and tertiary treatments (due in 2025) and quaternary treatments by 2045.¹⁹

Although EU Member States have gradually been upgrading WWTP infrastructure and their monitoring networks, institutional inertia stemming from previous (technically focused) water management regimes is a barrier to shifting towards more holistic policies (Martinez Fernandez et al., 2020). In addition, the actual monitoring methodologies applied in EU Member States are heterogeneous and mostly project-based, lacking a database to harmonize these findings and facilitate challenging reporting to the supranational level (Cipolletta et al., 2021). A recent study by the network of European Water Regulators has highlighted the lack of comparable information regarding the implementation of directives across the EU member states (see WAREG (2017)). Additionally, critical information on water systems is not collected or publicly available in countries such as Spain and Italy (World Bank Group, 2019). Moreover, authorities have limited capacity to monitor illegal intakes and discharges, a common issue in countries such as Spain, Portugal, and Italy.

MAR implementation sites would benefit from a numerical modeling component that enables groundwater flow analysis including solute transport and recharge assessment and groundwater recharge assessment across diverse climate change scenarios (and their impacts on dependent ecosystems). This methodological approach indicates the eventual consequences of climate change in the projected time series. In addition, it can analyze pollution risks and their impact on water systems. This approach is highly relevant, as RBMPs request forecasting scenarios of more than 20 years. However, most of these activities are carried out on a project basis (mainly EU funded projects), and there is no publicly available database to collect, harmonize, and publish this information. Most countries have noticed the lack of monitoring and control data, and in the case of EU Member States, this has been the basis for non-compliance with this WFD requirement.

5.7. Navigating MAR-related policy complexity and implementation

A particular challenge regarding water policy related to MAR is the case-by-case implementation of MAR; not only do aquifer characteristics and the essential local conditions (i.e., local meteorological conditions, soil type, and land use) differ, requiring a site-by-site approach, but MAR implementation also differs with respect to the source of water, including use of reclaimed water, and intended water reuse. The EU water policy framework still does not adequately harmonize or directly address the variety of MAR schemes. Therefore, although no explicit policy framework addresses MAR per se, several EU-level policies address MAR and related issues concerning reclaimed source water and

¹⁹ UWWTD evaluation was done in 2019, and reports on integrated management plans should be reviewed every 6 years (in alignment with the WFD).

its reuse (e.g., GWD, the UWWTD recast, and IED).

Licenses and permits are another instrument stated in the WFD to regulate MAR, and the EU Member States, through their RBMPS, are the implementers. However, according to reports in the literature, the process of assigning these licenses and providing permits remains unclear. Rossetto (2015) identifies the uncertainty regarding licensing procedures as well as a lack of licenses as a barrier to MAR implementation in Italy, while Bixio et al. (2006) identified cases in which licenses and permits are given (too) easily at the local level without control over the status of the aquifer reserves and control over the consumption of groundwater.

6. Conclusions

The paper has presented an analysis of the main EU water policies that govern the implementation of MAR, particularly those that allow the use of reclaimed water as a source water, whose use is not explicitly included (or excluded) in the EU water policy framework. It constitutes a first step in mapping the current water policy framework governing MAR and the use of reclaimed water as source water. Further empirical work is needed to explore the role of practices that effectively function as law in action for the local implementation of MAR and the reuse of reclaimed water as source water.

In order to facilitate the implementation of MAR systems across Europe, our findings translate into five key actions at EU level: (1) recognition of MAR practices within the GWD and related directives explicitly; (2) harmonization across lists of pollutants in the EU water policy framework regarding the purpose of water reuse, including for MAR; (3) a coherent and inter-operational risk monitoring strategy (and infrastructure) across Member States; (4) clear licensing and operational procedures (harmonized) across Member States to facilitate the current bottleneck in the local/regional implementation of MAR; and (5) clarity across the different directives in the promotion of reclaimed water as source water for MAR.

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During the preparation of this work, the authors used Grammarly in order to improve readability and language. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication. In addition, the graphical abstract was generated with researchviz.io and further modified and adjusted using MS Power Point.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bertha Vallejo: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Uta Wehn:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Brindhya Karthikeyan:** Writing – review & editing, Validation.

Declaration of competing interest

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article

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